

SOCIAL FUNCTIONS OF TOURISM/ HUMANISTIC FUNCTION OF TOURISM

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Annotation. *One of the components of humanistic education is education in the field of tourism. The humanistic function of tourism is determined by the fact that tourism is viewed as a means of interpersonal relations, as a form of interpersonal communications. The article shows that tourism is a product of a long cultural and historical development, shows the cultural and spiritual significance of tourism, its impact on the development of the student as an individual.*

Keywords: *culture, humanistic function of tourism, physical and cultural development.*

The system of knowledge, value-normative attitudes, principles of thinking and activity that determine the worldview of the first half of the XXI century, the dynamics of modernization processes is conditioned by global trends in the development of society and the state. World values based on the principles of tolerance are being formed. Globalization unites everyone irrespective of national, territorial and other peculiarities, separate social groups, cultural policy of separate states, etc. Therefore, the world community recognizes that in order to bring value orientations to everyone, it is important to create a unified global education system where everyone can get the necessary information. The characterization of the current socio-cultural situation in Uzbekistan is connected with the prospects of the dynamics of transformation of the social structure, including the transformation of the educational system.

Globalization leads to the need to include humanistic values in the education system, since with the introduction of new technologies and teaching methods, the spiritual, moral and aesthetic values of a person are leveled out.

The cultural level of modern society is determined by the peculiarity and quality of such areas as science, art, education. Education today is one of the necessary conditions for progress in all spheres. Education has an impact on all aspects of the life of any country, showing the level of intellectual development of society, which is primarily manifested in art, culture, education and each individual person.

In the system of education, the main task is to form values based on humanistic ideas, in the education of ethical, moral, spiritual foundations of human life, affecting the development of personality. Personality means a harmoniously developed, spiritual and moral person with humanistic values. Education, in fact, is a value itself, so the main problem of the state to create equal opportunities for all residents and make it available and real regardless of economic opportunities of a person. Humanism and education should be inextricably linked, as the value of education lies in its global, state, social and personal significance. Today this is understood by all countries, but not always solved due to political, economic and other reasons.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" defines education as "a purposeful process of education and training in the interests of a person, society, and the state, accompanied by a statement of achievement by a citizen (student) of the educational levels (educational qualifications) established by the state" [1].

As a result of the indicated directions, the humanities solve the problem of fostering a tolerant relationship between individuals, subcultures, states and nations on the basis of

knowledge. In the education system, not only knowledge should be given, conditions for the development of personality should be created equally, because only knowledge can give a person the opportunity to choose. The choice of his life priorities based on humanitarian values.

The gap between knowledge and human values can have a detrimental effect not only on the state of education as a whole, which will alienate already different civilizations and create crisis situations.

One of the components of humanistic education is education in the field of tourism.

The humanistic function of tourism is determined by the fact that we consider tourism as a means of interpersonal relations, as a form of interpersonal communication. It has the following derivatives:

- The ideological function, which consists in the fact that the worldview of society turns out to be in tourism. One cannot agree with the expression that tourism is beyond ideology. Preparation for tourism should be combined with the preparation of a citizen to fulfill his civic duty. Preparation for tourist practice, vacations and travel is part of the process of educating young people. This is both for the world to see and to show oneself.

- The political function of tourism, which is due to the fact that it not only contributes to the cultural enrichment of nations, but is also an effective means of establishing peaceful relations between countries and the social progress of mankind.

- The essence of the ethical function of tourism is the balance of differences in the socio-cultural traditions and customs of the peoples of the world, in promoting the realization of the rights of each person in the directions and forms of tourist activity. Modern tourism has become a factor of social balance, mutual understanding between people and nations and personal development.

In addition to well-known economic aspects, tourism acquires cultural and spiritual significance.

It is widely known that tourism carries a huge socio-cultural potential and is, above all, an important element of not only physical, but also environmental, moral, aesthetic and other spheres of culture [2].

Traveling is a pedagogical factor. On any trip, even a business trip, a person gets impressions and knowledge, mobilizes attention, thinking, memory, experiences a lot of emotions, develops communicability, sociability.

In essence, tourism is a powerful tool for education, enlightenment and experiential (i.e. experience-based) education, including humanistic education.

Children, teenagers and young people are born "tourists". The nature itself gives them curiosity and the desire to explore new territories and culture. The cultural, humanistic value of tourism is significantly influenced by the peculiarities of consciousness (interests, attitudes, value orientations, etc.) of those people who are involved in tourism activities, strive to use it for certain purposes, organize these activities and competitions in tourism.

Pedagogical factors of tourism are diverse. This is due to the presence of a large number of forms and types of tourism.

The main factors of tourism work are the following:

- emotional influence;
- tourist communication;
- self-activity;
- recreationality.

Speech, print, visual means are the main "carriers" of emotional impact. None of these means is universal: in tourism work they are used in combination with each other. It should be noted that in the work of the university departments, methodological developments that are well-tested in practice are used (these are field trips, excursions, including organized by the students themselves).

Tourist communication is aimed at joint mastering and exchange of tourism values by participants. In tourism activity it is manifested in selective and voluntary contacts, namely in regular lectures and practical classes. The most important aspect of tourist work is social creativity, inherent to a greater or lesser extent in almost all tourist activities and especially active in tourist troupes. Their daily life itself produces and develops unselfishness, humanity, collectivism, desire and ability to cooperate, to help friends.

Tourism with its rich content of various actions (self-service, overcoming various obstacles and life difficulties, testing knowledge, skills, abilities, etc.), is an excellent means of self-education, which is based on the need for a person to "turn on" volitional efforts. The latter are associated with muscle tension, attention strain, overcoming fatigue, feelings of fear, uncertainty, compliance with a certain mode of travel. One of the functions of tourism is to relieve fatigue, to give a person physical and psychological discharge, which contributes to the recovery and further development of its physical and spiritual forces. It should be taken into account and factors of a wider purpose, namely: change of occupation (the most universal factor of rest); relaxed and unregulated communication; movement; socially useful work for the time of tourist events. What is important here is that tourist work is quite diverse and combines the satisfaction of people's needs for recreation and healthy entertainment with enlightenment and educational tasks [3].

It follows from mentioned above that tourism is not only an important part of students' education system, but also influences their physical and cultural development. Tourism contributes to the comprehensive and harmonious development of man, which confirms the need for a wide spread of tourism and the use of not only traditional, but also new forms of its organization. Forms can be different: from one-day hikes to the organization of complex multidimensional tourist and cultural events. Practice shows that young people's interest in such forms of tourism organization is significant and in some cases tends to increase.

Tourism is a product of long cultural and historical development. It existed long before our era, and its formation and development are closely connected with the history of society. The higher the level of development of society, the more developed types and forms of tourism in it arise, which, in turn, makes it possible to reveal to a greater extent for people its cultural value and humanistic orientation. Nowadays in the world there is a whole "industry" of tourism with a huge variety of forms of realization of cultural needs of a person: aesthetic, health-improving, cognitive and others.

Tourism activities contribute to the comprehensive and harmonious development of the mankind, its humanistic component, which confirms the need for a wide dissemination of tourism and the use of not only traditional but also new forms of its organization.

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